

Electrical Testing Handout

Your tools :

In the box you should find :

- 1- A Black Cable
- 2- A Red Cable
- 3- A Multimeter

Step 1 : Prepare your workspace

- 1 – Plug the Black probe in the **COM** port
- 2 – Plug the Red probe in the **VΩmA** port

Your workspace should look like this

*Note: Make sure that the cables are well plugged –
Please double check*

Step 2 : Switch on the Multimeter

Switch on the Multimeter :

- A- Turn the knob from position 1 to 2 to switch on the multimeter and choose the setting.
- B- Verify that the setting is correct : the screen should display 200 (3)

Step 3 : Do the measurements

To do the electrical testing you will have to place the probes in the position indicated by orange arrows.

- 1- Place the Black probe under the electrode

- 2 – Place the Red probe on the fastener

3- This is a picture of how the electrical testing should be done. The value displayed on screen will have to be reported (see step 4)

Note : Hold each probe with your hands to make sure that the probe is touching the right surface and that the electrodes is stable.

Step 4 : Report your measures

You will have to do 20 measures per electrodes and report the values in the table below.

Important:

The measured value should be under 20 Ohms.

The values for different electrodes should be similar.

If not, ask a supervisor at the workshop.

Warning:

Hold 1 probe with 1 hand! The probes have to be stable during the measurements, use both hands.

Correct measures are displayed on the right side of the screen.

Incorrect measures are displayed on the left side of the screen. It means that the device has a problem or a wrong setting, please call a supervisor.

Correct measure

Incorrect measure

M\E	E01	E02	E03	E04	E05	E06	E07	E08	E09	E10	E11	E12
M01												
M02												
M03												
M04												
M05												
M06												
M07												
M08												
M09												
M10												
M11												
M12												
M13												
M14												
M15												
M16												
M17												
M18												
M19												
M20												

M: measurement number

E: electrode number